

Studies on Stereochemical Reaction in Heterocyclic Compounds. Part II. Stereochemical Conversion of Yohimbine to β -Yohimbine*

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Epimerization of yohimbine to β -yohimbine has been achieved in presence of alkoxide ions and carbonyl reagents in hydroxylic and nonpolar solvents. This steric change is explainable by a two-step mechanism.

In an earlier publication (Chatterjee and Ghosal, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 545), studies on the behaviour of yohimbine and rauwolfscione towards complex metal hydrides were reported. The present communication describes the steric course of epimerization of yohimbine to β -yohimbine in presence of basic catalysts and hydrogen acceptors in non-polar and hydroxylic solvents. The proposed mechanism of stereochemical conversion has been found to be consistent with the experimental evidences and is similar to that proposed by Doering and his associates (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1700).

Based on this concept, we have been able to equilibrate yohimbine and obtained β -yohimbine under varying experimental conditions.**

The first step of this reaction is assumed to involve oxidation of yohimbine (I) to yohimbineone (II) by a carbonyl compound, e.g., fluorenone in presence of alkali alkoxides.

This reaction is thus similar to oxidation-reduction equilibrium between alcohol-ketone systems catalysed by an alkoxide ion (Ponndorf, *Angew. Chem.*, 1926, 39, 139).

Subsequent conversion of the ketone (II) to β -yohimbine (III) involves either its stereospecific reduction with sodium borohydride (Chatterjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) or its reduction by alkoxide ions in corresponding alcoholic solvents to yield the more stable epimer (III).

* Addendum: Since the communication of this paper a publication on similar studies (Janot, Goutarel, Warnhoff, and Le Hir, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1961, 3, 637) has appeared.

** cf. Ghosal and Chatterjee, *Proc. Ind. Sci. Cong.*, 1960, Part III, 143.

(III)

This second operation in conjunction with the previous one completes the epimerization of yohimbine to β -yohimbine.

Reduction of ketones by alcohols in presence of alkoxides is well known ("Meerwein-Ponndorf reduction", A. L. Wilds, "Organic Reactions", Vol. II, J. Wiley & Sons, N.Y., 1944, p. 178). Besides, there are a number of references in which sodium alkoxide effects reduction of ketones (Rubin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 2075). Transformation of yohimbinone to β -yohimbine, as stated above, is an exemplification of these observations (*loc. cit.*).

It was found (Doering *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) that carbonyl compounds (capable of producing diastereomeric alcohols) on reduction with alcohols in presence of the corresponding alkoxides gave a mixture of epimers. Yohimbinone behaved similarly and yielded a mixture of yohimbine and β -yohimbine when reduced under similar conditions. The mixture thus obtained was subsequently separated into two homogeneous components by chromatographic resolution.

In further support of the validity of the proposed oxidation-reduction mechanism of equilibration might be mentioned the behaviour of quinine and quinone (Doering *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) towards tertiary alcohols. According to the mechanism cited above, ketones should be incapable of reduction by tertiary alcohols, the latter being incapable of oxidation by the ketones. In consonance with this conclusion, quinone was found to be completely stable in a solution of potassium butoxide^t in butanol^t under reflux condition. Despite several other instances, which support this generalisation, yohimbine was claimed to undergo a single-step epimerization to β -yohimbine (Le Hir and Warnhoff, *Compt. rend.*, 1958, **246**, 1564) with potassium butoxide^t in dry benzene. We could not, however, effect such equilibration under similar experimental conditions. In fact, only a sluggish disproportionation was observed when yohimbine was refluxed with this alkoxide in the corresponding alcohol, resulting in a small amount of yohimbinone (1.02%).

Another important factor that has been considered for the degree of the above transformation (I-III) is the role of carbonyl reagents. Fluorenone exhibited a definite improvement over benzophenone. Thus, boiled for 45 hours with 1, 2, and 5 equivalents of the latter in a solution of sodium methoxide in benzene, yohimbine was converted to yohimbinone in yields of 3, 5, and 8% respectively. When similarly treated with 2 equivalents of the rapid oxidising agent, like fluorenone, yohimbine produced the desired ketone in 70% yield.

An interesting difference in the rate of oxidation (I-II) was also observed when sodium was replaced with potassium. The formation of yohimbine (70%) in presence of sodium methoxide required 20 hours; whereas the optimum time for oxidation was only 8 hours with the corresponding potassium alkoxide. Since the transformation reaction requires catalytic action of strong bases (Doering *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), the increased rate of reaction in presence of potassium alkoxide may be ascribed to the weaker conjugate acidity of the potassium ion in comparison with the more acidic sodium ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxidation of Yohimbine to Yohimbine.—A mixture of yohimbine (0.5 g.), sodium methoxide (0.1 g.), and fluorenone (0.2 g.) in dry benzene (500 c.c.) was refluxed for 20 hours when yohimbine sodium enolate separated from the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice, and extracted with 5% HCl (40 c.c.). The acid extract was cooled in ice and basified with ice-cold liquor ammonia (*pH* 7.5–8). Yohimbine, precipitated as a pale yellow solid, was extracted with chloroform. The aqueous layer was salted and re-extracted with chloroform. The combined chloroform extracts (150 c.c.) were washed with water (saturated with sodium chloride), dried, and evaporated on a water bath (0.42 g.). The residue was crystallised from ethanol in long, pale yellow needles, m.p. 255–56° (decomp.). (Found in a dry sample: C, 71.48; H, 7.33; N, 7.78. $C_{21}H_{24}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.39; H, 6.82; N, 7.95%.)

The above process of oxidation was repeated with several other alkoxides and carbonyl reagents. The results obtained from these operations have already been recorded (*vide supra*).

2, 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of Yohimbine.—To a solution of yohimbine (50 mg.) in aldehyde-free ethanol (20 c. c.) was added a solution of 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine sulphate (20 mg.) in the same solvent (10 c.c.). The mixture was concentrated when D.N.P.H. of yohimbine separated. Crystallisation from ethanol yielded orange-red needles, m.p. 288–90°. (Found in a dry sample: N, 15.42. $C_{21}H_{28}O_6N_6$ requires N, 15.78%.)

Reduction of Yohimbine to β -Yohimbic Acid.—To a well-cooled solution of yohimbine (0.2 g.) in moist methanol (50 c. c.) a solution of sodium borohydride (0.1 g.) in the same solvent (dry) was slowly added. The solution was kept at room temperature overnight. On removing the solvent a residue was left which was subsequently decomposed with ice-cold water (10 c. c.) and then acidified with acetic acid (*pH* 5.5–6.0). The mixture was extracted with ether (25 c. c. $\times$ 4). Ether extract was washed with water, dried, and concentrated. Crude residue on crystallisation from methanol gave pure β -yohimbic acid, m.p. 261–63°. (Found in a dry sample: C, 70.36; H, 7.20; N, 8.43. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$: C, 70.60; H, 7.06; N, 8.23%.)

Esterification of β -Yohimbic Acid to β -Yohimbine.—Crude β -yohimbic acid (0.1 g.) was dissolved in dry methanol (50 c.c.), cooled in a freezing bath, and dry HCl gas was passed through it till saturation. The solution was kept at room temperature overnight. It was then warmed on a steam bath to expel excess of HCl gas and the solvent was removed under suction. Crystallisation of the corresponding base from methanol yielded β -yohimbine (50 mg.), m.p. 237–38°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of β -yohimbine, 2CH₃OH remained undepressed. (Found in a dry sample: C, 71.04; H, 7.18; N, 7.82. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2$: C, 71.18; H, 7.34; N, 7.90%.)

Reduction of Yohimbinone with Alkoxides.—Yohimbinone (200 mg.) was gently refluxed in a solution of dry sodium ethoxide (1 g.) in absolute ethanol (50 c.c.) for 15 hours. The solvent was removed in *vacuo* and the residue triturated with 5*N*-HCl (25 c.c.). The aqueous acid solution was then basified and extracted with chloroform (20 c.c. × 3). The chloroform extract was washed with water, dried to a small volume, and concentrated. The mixture of crude bases separating was purified by chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina (2 g.) using a mixture of methanol and acetone as the solvent and the eluent as well. The eluates were collected in fraction of 25 c. c. portions and evaporated to dryness (Table I).

TABLE I

Eluents.	Fraction collected.	Residue.	$[\alpha]^{28}$ (pyridine).
Acetone 98% Methanol 2	1—5	Negligible	..
Acetone 95% Methanol 5	6—9	Yohimbine (85 mg.) m.p. 232°	+98 ± 1°
Acetone 80% Methanol 20	10—15	β-Yohimbine (78 mg.) m.p. 238°	-53 ± 1°

The above experimental method for the reduction of yohimbinone to β-yohimbine was adopted with other alkoxides resulting in varying degrees of success (*vide supra*).

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